

BEYOND THE TEXTBOOK: INTEGRATING WEB TECHNOLOGY TO DEVELOP 21ST-CENTURY SKILLS THROUGH DISCOURSE ANALYSIS

Abduramanova Nezire Enverovna

The Teacher of Department of Integrated English Language,
Uzbek State World Languages University, Tashkent, Republic of Uzbekistan
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Abstract

The contemporary landscape demands individuals equipped with 21st-century skills – critical thinking, communication, collaboration, and digital literacy. Discourse analysis, a discipline that examines the structure and function of language in social contexts, provides an ideal platform to cultivate these skills. Web technology can be integrated into discourse analysis instruction, transforming classrooms into dynamic environments where students develop essential 21st-century competencies.

Keywords: discourse analysis, web technology, competence, skills, platform, enhance, integrated, classroom

Абстракт

Современный мир требует от людей навыков 21 века - критического мышления, коммуникации, сотрудничества и цифровой грамотности. Дискурс-анализ, дисциплина, изучающая структуру и работу языка в социальных контекстах, представляет собой идеальную платформу для развития этих навыков. Веб-технологии можно интегрировать в преподавание дискурс-анализа, превратив класс в динамичную среду, где студенты развивают важнейшие компетенции XXI века.

The world is changing at an unprecedented pace, demanding individuals equipped with a new set of skills to navigate a complex and interconnected world. These 21st-century skills – critical thinking, communication, collaboration, and digital literacy – are essential for success in a rapidly evolving world. While traditional education has long focused on foundational knowledge and skills, it's increasingly crucial to incorporate innovative approaches that foster these crucial 21st-century competencies.

Discourse analysis, the study of language in social contexts, offers a rich platform to cultivate these skills. Examining how language is used to construct meaning, persuade, and influence, discourse analysis encourages critical thinking, effective communication, and a nuanced understanding of social dynamics. However, traditional teaching methods can often fall short in

engaging students and providing the dynamic learning experiences necessary to truly develop these skills.

This is where web technology enters the equation. By integrating web-based tools and platforms into discourse analysis instruction, we can create dynamic and engaging learning environments that equip students with the critical thinking, communication, collaboration, and digital literacy skills they need to thrive in the 21st century. This presentation will explore the innovative ways web technology can transform discourse analysis instruction, empowering students to become active participants in their learning journey and fostering the skills essential for success in a world where communication and critical thinking are paramount.

Online platforms facilitate critical thinking through interactive activities that challenge students to analyze texts from diverse perspectives. Moreover, students can analyze social media posts, online articles, or forum discussions to identify bias, hidden agendas, and persuasive techniques. In addition, virtual forums and collaborative platforms allow students to engage in structured debates and discussions, exploring different interpretations of texts and refining their analytical arguments. Besides that, Web technology creates opportunities for students to practice communication skills in various modalities.

Online platforms like Google Docs allow students to collaborate on writing projects, providing opportunities for constructive feedback and refining their communication styles. Students can create digital presentations, video essays, or podcasts, honing their skills in visual communication, storytelling, and audience engagement. Online platforms also foster a collaborative learning environment, encouraging students to work together and build upon each other's ideas. Finally, Students can engage in online brainstorming sessions, work collaboratively on research projects, and share insights through shared document editing. Online discussion forums and feedback tools facilitate peer-to-peer interaction, promoting constructive criticism and collective learning.

Conclusion

By embracing web technology, educators can transform discourse analysis instruction into a dynamic and engaging experience that cultivates valuable 21st-century skills. Interactive platforms, diverse resources, and collaborative tools empower students to think critically, communicate effectively, collaborate effectively, and become proficient digital citizens, preparing them for success. Discourse analysis, with its focus on critical thinking, communication, and understanding social dynamics, provides an ideal framework for cultivating

these skills. However, traditional methods often fall short in capturing student engagement and fostering the dynamic learning experiences required for true mastery.

By integrating web technology into discourse analysis instruction, we can bridge this gap and create transformative learning environments. Interactive online platforms, diverse resources, and collaborative tools empower students to think critically, communicate effectively, collaborate seamlessly, and become proficient digital citizens.

This approach goes beyond simply delivering information; it fosters active learning, promotes critical thinking, and equips students to navigate the complexities of the 21st century. As we continue to embrace the potential of web technology, we can ensure that discourse analysis education empowers students to become informed, engaged, and successful members of a rapidly changing world.

Discourse Analysis: A Resource Book for Students" by J. Flowerdew (Book providing a comprehensive introduction to discourse analysis with practical activities)

References:

The handbook of research on teaching discourse analysis. Routledge. Butt, D. C. C., Fairclough, C. R. R., & Lillis, G. W. (Eds.). (2017).

"Web 2.0 and classroom learning: Concepts, contexts, and applications. Thomas, Routledge. M. F. (2011).

Discourse analysis: A resource book for students. Flowerdew, J. Routledge. (2014).